

TYPES OF SPEECH. CLASSIFICATION OF STYLISTIC DEVICES.
LEXICAL STYLISTIC DEVICE: METAPHOR, METONYMY.

Mirzaaliyeva Maftuna Ulfat qizi

4rd year student at Djizzak branch of National University
of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

Supervisor: **Zilola Abdurakhmanova**

Assistant teacher in the department of Foreign languages at Djizzak
branch of National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek

Annotation

This article presents the information about metaphor and metonymy is regarded as a tool for promoting linguistics and semiotics. This paper sets out to discuss the types of speech classification of stylistic device, metaphor and metonymy. In doing the discussion, the essay is divided into three sections. The first section provides an introduction with an attempt to provide scholarly definitions of the key terms; the second section gives examples. The final section provides a viable conclusion. The thesis of this paper is that illustrates information about stylistic device.

Key words: Types of Speech, Lexical Stylistic Device, Lexical meaning.

The communication takes place in different forms and situations. According to the situation in which the communication proceeds we distinguish two types of speech: oral and written which are characterised by a number of typical features. The oral communication proceeds in the presence of interlocutor, the main form of it is a dialogue. The written communication, does not require any interlocutor, its main form is a monologue. The oral type of speech is more expressive and emotional. It involves such powerful means of expressiveness as gestures, mimicry, intonation, pitch, melody, stress and the others, which apart from language means can express much: joy or sorrow, hate or love, consent or denial. As Bernard Shaw said: There are 500 ways of saying "no" but only one way to put it down. The oral types of speech differs from the written language phonetically, morphologically, lexically and syntactically. 1. Of morphological forms the spoken language commonly uses contracted forms: can't, shan't. I'll, don't, won't and so on, which are dictated by a quick tempo of the oral type of speech. 2. At the lexical there is a number of peculiarities typical of the oral type: 1) a great number of words and phrases typically colloquial: kid, chap, daddy are used in colloquial speech to introduce statements. 2) the use of special words and phrases which are used in colloquial speech to introduce statements. For example the use of interjection why, which can express objection, reflection, impatience, surprise. Why, his just being in a lab is a prayer "Say", "I say", "Look here" are also used at the

beginning of a sentence to call attention to what is about to follow, sometimes it is used as an exclamation, thus tending to become an interjection. Say, if you don't like the way we study medicine. Look here! We don't tell you how you ought to work. 3. The use of cut words - curtails: phone, lab, gent, prof, doc, dele, bike, exam and so on. 4. There is another characteristic feature of colloquial language, that is, the insertion into the utterance of words without any meaning which are called "fill ups" or empty words. To some extent they give a touch of completing to the sentence if used at the end of it, or if used in the middle, help the speaker to fill the gap when unable to find the proper word. Such words and set expressing as: well, so to say, you know, you understand, you see belong to the category of "fill ups". The syntactical peculiarities of the spoken language are the following:

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